

MULTISCALE ENTHESES MECHANICS

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ABSTRACT

The tendon-to-bone insertion site (enthesis) represents a fascinating example of a multiscale natural optimization of the joint between composite orthotropic (tendon) and composite isotropic (bone) tissues with vastly different properties. The composition and properties of tendon vary in a narrow region adjacent to bone. The result is an optimized attachment possessing desirable strength, stiffness and toughness. The multifunctional optimization is achieved through material and morphological grading occurring on nanoscale, microscale and macroscale. The effectiveness and response of the enthesis are affected by its mechanics on all these scales.

In this paper, we outline mechanical issues pertinent to multiscale mechanics of enthesis concentrating on state-of-the art knowledge as well as pressing issues that should be addressed to properly and accurately model enthesis. We demonstrate aspects of mechanics on several scales that contribute to an optimized insertion site. In case of a post-trauma healing, recovered insertion site does not exhibit such optimization as is reflected in high repeated failure rates that can reach up to 94% in certain populations. Therefore, the multiscale mechanical analysis of the tendon-to-bone insertion site can help in developing restorative surgical protocols and postoperative therapy. Such knowledge is also helpful for biomimetic engineering solutions aimed at joining of dissimilar materials.

1 INTRODUCTION

The tendon-to-bone insertion site represents a unique example of a biological attachment of two composite materials. While the modulus of elasticity of the bone is of an order of 20GPa , the longitudinal and transverse moduli of the tendon are of order of 450MPa and 40MPa , respectively. The attachment occurs over the insertion site of a very small length (less than 1mm in humans and much smaller in such animals as mice). Considering significant force that has to be transmitted between the tendon and bone, the strength and toughness of the insertion site are paramount. Several problems addressed studying the insertion site include understanding of the means by which nature achieves the optimum attachment between such dissimilar materials as tendon and bone, observations and conclusions that could be useful for a development of efficient surgical protocols, and a development of therapies both sustaining the healthy insertion as well as facilitating its postsurgical healing. Extensive research of the tendon-to-bone insertion site, including the studies cited below, has demonstrated that the optimization of the insertion is achieved through numerous interacting

mechanisms on several scales, including nanoscale ($10^{-9} m$), microscale ($10^{-6} m$) and macroscale ($10^{-3} m$). The goal of this paper is to outline and summarize our findings, and to suggest several studies useful for a better understanding of mechanics of the insertion site and for further application of this knowledge to both medical as well as engineering problems involving attachments of dissimilar materials.

Four regions constitute the tendon-to-bone insertion site: adjacent tendon, unmineralized and mineralized fibrocartilage, and bone (Fig. 1). The analysis of mechanics of the site is primarily concerned with unmineralized and mineralized fibrocartilage consisting of collagen fibers bonded by proteoglycans and of mineral deposits with the concentration increasing from the boundary between unmineralized and mineralized tissues to bone.

The nanoscale analysis involves the characterization of collagen molecules, fibrils and fibers and modelling mineral deposits in and around the fibrils and fibers from tendon to bone. The highest scale is represented by triple helix collagen molecules that are organized in quarter-stagger fibrils forming the fiber. Mineral accumulates in the gaps between molecules and around the fibrils forming a sheath around the latter in the vicinity to bone.

At the microscale level, two gradients combine resulting in a functionally graded material. One is related to the orientation of collagen fibers that varies in the vicinity to bone. Combined with the mineral gradient, such grading results in a compliant band with lower stiffness than those of either tendon or bone. Presumably, the function of such low stiffness band is an increased toughness of the insertion site. In addition, the waviness of the boundaries between bone and mineralized fibrocartilage and between mineralized and unmineralized fibrocartilage enhances toughness at the expense of higher stresses. The macroscopic mechanics of the insertion site is related to its morphology and to a potential benefit of the low-stiffness band for a reduction of the stress concentration.

Fig. 1. Histological tissue section of enthesis at the rotator cuff of a mouse. Section stained in black corresponds to a mineralized fibrocartilage. The bottom left section is the bone. The section at the right top of the figure is tendon and the pinkish section corresponds to unmineralized cartilage.

2. MULTISCALE ANALYSIS OF ENTHESES

2.1. Nanoscale insight

Collagen fibers are complex structures formed by collagen molecules consisting of three left-handed amino acid chains making a right-handed helix [1]. Each molecule has the length of

approximately 300 nm and diameter of 1.5 nm. Collagen molecules arranged in a staggered quaternary pattern form fibrils that in turn constitute collagen fibers where cross-linking is provided by proteoglycans.

At the fibril scale, collagen molecules are arranged in a staggered pattern schematically shown in Fig. 2. The stagger spacing (D -spacing) has been measured, approximately being equal to 67 nm. Consecutive molecules are separated by 35 to 40 nm gaps [2], [3]. The space between collagen molecules within the fibril is filled with water and intermolecular crosslinks built of non-collagenous proteins. Modelling nanomechanics of the insertion site involves several aspects, including the characterization of protein molecules, fibrils and fibers as well as the accumulation of mineral and its effect on the mechanical characteristics of the fiber.

Tendons consist of well aligned collagen fibers in the matrix that contains water and proteoglycan links between the fibers. In the vicinity to bone, mineral deposits are present, with the concentration increasing from the boundary between unmineralized and mineralized fibrocartilage to bone. Although the sustainment of mineral in the body requires the presence of mechanical stress, soft enthesis tissues are mineralized in the post-natal phase under low stresses as a result of high stress concentration around chondrocyte cells [4]. Two factors contributing to the stress concentration were identified. They are associated with global concentration attributed to vastly different tendon, insertion and bone properties and local stress concentration around chondrocytes that disappear with age, but not before resulting in high stresses facilitating mineral deposition at the post-natal phase of life. In this paper, we consider mature enthesis where the gradient, distribution and geometry of mineral deposits that greatly affect the performance do not change with time.

Even at the highest scale molecular level, nonlocal elastic effects may alter the stiffness found from molecular dynamics simulations or by interpreting the results of representative experiments. In a recent paper, though, these effects were shown small [5]. The phenomenon that has a more prominent impact on the mechanical properties of the insertion site is the sequence of bioapatite (mineral) accumulation throughout the mineralized section of the fibrocartilage, from the boundary with the unmineralized fibrocartilage to the boundary with the bone where the volume fraction of mineral reaches 50%. Detailed analysis of possible scenarios of progressive collagen stiffening by bioapatite is presented in a recent paper [3]. There are five possible accumulation scenarios dependent on the sequence of progressive mineralization as the volume fraction of bioapatite increases from unmineralized fibrocartilage to bone (e.g., filling the gaps prior to forming extrafibrillar sheath or random deposits on the fibril surface followed with filling the gaps and forming a solid extrafibrillar sheath, etc.). The sequence of mineralization has been shown to significantly affect the local stiffness tensor of the insertion as reflected in Fig. 3.

Fig. 2. Schematics of collagen molecules forming the fibril. Molecules are shown in a staggered pattern, the stagger distance $D \approx 0.67 \text{ nm}$. The gap region $e \approx 0.6D$. Bioapatite (mineral) can initially accumulate in the gap region, in the overlap regions or extrafibrillarly. Different mineral accumulation sequences affect the stiffness of the fibril. Not shown: extrafibrillar mineral.

Although we lack sufficient molecular simulation or experimental data on local stiffness of the insertion site to correlate with the results shown in Fig. 3 and accordingly, specify the actual sequence of mineralization, the presence of a compliant zone adjacent to the boundary between unmineralized and mineralized insertion has been documented [6]. Accordingly, model D predicting an abrupt rise of the stiffness tensor is less likely to represent the actual insertion than other models that produce rather

close results. This implies that mineralization begins within the fibril, rather than in the form of random extrafibrillar patches as assumed in model D. Other important problems relevant to nanoscale analysis of the enthesis include stress transfer between fibers and between fibrils within the fiber, characterization of “matrix” within the fibers and fibrils, etc.

Fig. 3. Variations of longitudinal modulus of elasticity from tendon to bone dependent on the sequence of fibril mineralization by several representative models. Model A: mineral accumulates in the gaps prior to uniform extrafibrillar mineralization; Model B: mineral accumulates in the gaps, followed with extrafibrillar mineralization originating from a single nucleation site on each fibril; Model C: mineral accumulates in the gaps, followed with random extrafibrillar accumulation; Model D: random extrafibrillar mineralization, followed with filling of the gaps.

2.2. Microscale functional grading and interdigitation at the insertion site

Two different functional grading contributions combine at the microscale optimizing the response of the insertion site [7], [8] and [9]. Collagen fibers that are predominantly aligned in the tendon demonstrate much higher direction variability within fibrocartilage. This results in a loss of stiffness and presumably contributes to the observed local compliant belt near the boundary between unmineralized and mineralized fibrocartilage whose function may be higher energy absorption. As indicated in the previous section, accumulation of bioapatite in the mineralized fibrocartilage involves nanoscale aspects associated with the sequence of its deposits and their progressive development. The micromechanical analysis has to account for experimentally confirmed grading of mineral and its effect on the mechanical response of the insertion site. While a deviation of the mean collagen fiber orientation from the tendon axis causes lower stiffness and enhanced energy absorption, the gradient of mineral results in a progressively increasing stiffness approaching the bone supposedly alleviating the stress concentration. These somewhat competing gradients are reflected in Fig. 4.

It has been observed that the interface between mineralized fibrocartilage and bone is rough, as demonstrated in Fig. 5. Such roughness seems counterintuitive since it undoubtedly contributes to local stress concentrations on the microscopic scale. Therefore, a study has recently been conducted elucidating the function of the roughness in the optimization of the insertion site [10].

Fig. 4. Relative mineral concentration based on Raman microprobe measurements shown on the left reflects a gradient from tendon to bone. The collagen fiber misalignment reaches maximum within the insertion, presumably contributing to the local dip in stiffness and enhanced toughness. From [8]; used with permission.

Fig. 5. Image of the tendon-to-bone attachment site of a mouse (left). Mineralized tissue is stained with black, the unmineralized tissue is purple. The Monte Carlo simulation employed in the analysis (right): cosine waves of identical length but varying amplitudes resemble the actual insertion. From [10]; used with permission.

The linear theory of elasticity perturbation solution was developed extrapolating the approach of Gao [11] and modelling the interface by a single cosine wave. This yielded the stresses throughout the interface and insertion enabling us to predict the loss of strength within each cosine wave where the amplitudes varied stochastically according to a normal distribution as justified by the analysis of experimental images. The outcome of our analysis demonstrated that while roughness contributes to the stress concentration and associated loss of strength, its positive contribution to the gain in toughness may be more important for the integrity of the insertion as shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. The strength loss and toughness gain dependent on the wave mean amplitude-to-length ratio (horizontal axis) and standard deviation (vertical axis). The physiological values shown for mice at 28 and 56 days after birth imply that the gain in toughness at the expense of lower strength contributes to an optimum insertion. From [10]; used with permission.

The validity of the approximate analysis based on the perturbation elasticity theory is limited by the constraint on the roughness amplitude to wave length ratio. Accordingly, the comparison to a finite element analysis was conducted for representative cases and resulted in the conclusion that as long as the amplitude-to-wave length ratio remains smaller than 0.2, the elasticity solution is accurate. Notably, such moderate interdigitation is in agreement with experimental observations for mice validating general conclusions from the study.

Further studies at the micromechanical scale of the insertion site should elucidate a more accurate gradient of bioapatite within the mineralized fibrocartilage as well as its location within the tissue (e.g., mineral forming bridges between fibers vs. accumulating on their surface). Such knowledge is necessary for the development of an accurate micromechanics pertinent to mineralized fibrocartilage. Furthermore, the strength and toughness analyses of a partially mineralized and unmineralized fibrocartilage would be useful for a better understanding of the optimization of the insertion site. Of course, this list of potential research subjects on the micromechanical scale could further be expanded.

2.3. Macroscale mechanics of enthesis

Several mechanisms contributing to the effectiveness and integrity of enthesis have been identified in our research (e.g., [9] [12]). They include a shallow attachment angle at the insertion site, i.e. optimum morphology, and alleviation of the stress concentration through a compliant zone (that also contributes to an enhanced toughness). For example, representing the rotator cuff as a system of three concentric rings with the solid inner core modelling bone encompassed within the insertion that is in turn encompassed within the cylindrically orthotropic tendon, it was found that a compliant insertion with the stiffness lower than those of tendon and bone may result in a complete elimination of stress concentrations at the macroscopic scale as shown in Fig. 7.

The optimum shape of the outward splay of the scar insertion tissue at the human supraspinatus tendon-to-bone rotator cuff was investigated in [12]. The damaged insertion is not reproduced upon healing leaving instead a much more vulnerable isotropic tissue. The analysis was concerned with finding the shape of the scar tissue resulting in a reduction in the peak principal stress. Notably, in the case of a scar tissue that is isotropic and homogeneous, a reduction in the maximum principal stress implies the improvement in strength.

Fig. 7. Concentration of the radial stress in the model of the insertion site can be completely eliminated as a result of the compliant zone between the tendon and bone. Two cases considered correspond to different major Poisson ratios of the insertion. From [9]; used with permission.

The model of the insertion site shown in Fig. 8 was subject to uniform tensile stress applied at the upper boundary; considering symmetry of the insertion, only one-half of it was analyzed. The tendon was modelled as an orthotropic material, while both the scar tissue and bone were isotropic. The study started with geometry shown on the left in Fig. 8 and after the iterations shown in this figure resulted in the optimum geometry shown on the right corresponding to the ratio of the peak principal stress to applied stress ratio equal to 1.05. The analysis elucidated that in case of naturally healed scar interfacial tissues a shallow attachment is beneficial. This interesting and somewhat counterintuitive observation may be useful developing restorative surgical protocols. Among possible future macromechanical studies of the insertion site we mention here an extension of [12] extrapolating the analysis to the intact functionally graded, orthotropic insertion site, contrary to the homogeneous, isotropic scar tissue. Furthermore, a study of morphology of the insertion site accounting for the effect of chondrocytes in the post-natal phase may be of interest.

9 CONCLUSIONS

The tendon-to-bone insertion site (enthesis) overcomes the challenge of the attachment of two dramatically dissimilar materials, tendon and bone, over a very short distance through a number of mechanisms acting on three different scales. In this paper we briefly overview some of the principal factors affecting the multiscale mechanics of enthesis.

At nanoscale, one of the principal effects on mechanics of the insertion site is associated with the sequence of accumulation of mineral deposits within and outside collagen fibrils, from the boundary of the unmineralized fibrocartilage to bone. Analyzing possible scenarios we observed that this sequence affects the local stiffness of the fibril. Accordingly, there is a link between the nanoscale mineral accumulation process and the subsequent microscale functional grading of the insertion that in turn affects its macroscale characteristics. Such interaction of different scale effects is particularly interesting since our studies demonstrated that the deposition of mineral in a post-natal insertion is affected by local stresses. Therefore, it is plausible that the interaction occurs over different scales, with the emphasis shifting from the microscale phenomena affecting nanoscale mechanics at the post-natal phase and reversing in the mature organism where nanoscale mineral distribution affects microscale parameters that influence the stiffness tensor.

Fig. 8. Successive geometries considered in the course of optimization of the scar insertion site. The ratio of the peak principal stress normalized with respect to the applied stress was reduced to 1.05 (geometry on the right).

Two functional grading mechanisms at the microscale level combine affecting toughness and stiffness of enthesis. While an elevated misalignment of collagen fibers in the vicinity to the boundary between unmineralized and mineralized fibrocartilage produces an experimentally verifiable zone of lower stiffness, a gradient of mineral concentration from zero in unmineralized fibrocartilage to nearly 50% volume fraction in the bone results in a progressively higher stiffness of the insertion site. We hypothesize that the low-stiffness zone contributes to enhanced toughness of enthesis and a lower stress concentration, while functional grading associated with the presence of bioapatite provides necessary strength and also reduces stress concentrations near bone (the stress concentration would be higher in case of an abrupt change in stiffness). The other factor affecting mechanics of the insertion site is the waviness (interdigitation) of the interfaces of the mineralized fibrocartilage. Although such interdigitation increases stress concentration, the negative effect of elevated stresses is compensated by the gain in toughness. Therefore, two microscale factors contributing to a higher toughness of the insertion site that have been identified are misalignment of collagen fibers and interdigitation along the boundary of mineralized fibrocartilage.

At the macromechanical scale, the properties acquired at a higher scale, such as micromechanical grading, produce some of desirable features of enthesis. It has already been mentioned that the presence of a compliant zone due to functional grading of collagen fibers and mineral deposits enhances toughness, while it may simultaneously result in a lower stress concentration. A potential implication of this observation on surgical protocols is understood in light of high repeated failure rate of post-surgical healed insertion sites where a compliant zone is not observed. In addition, our analysis of optimum geometries of the artificial insertion suggests that circular fillet geometry may be preferable to prismatic cross section of the insertion attached to the bone.

In conclusion, the tendon-to-bone insertion site or enthesis represents a unique composite joint between biological tissues where vastly dissimilar materials are joined over a very short distance. The optimization of the joint resulting in satisfactory strength, stiffness and toughness is achieved through a combination of factors on three different scales. Besides observations and conclusions that are useful for a development of better surgical protocols and therapies, lessons acquired from the study of the tendon-to-bone insertion site may prove valuable for a development of advanced engineering composite materials and joints.

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